

THE IMPACT OF GENDER APPROACHES ON EDUCATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract. *The article covers the impact of gender approaches on educational effectiveness on the basis of statistical and scientific data, and the need to rely on the basis of the necessary knowledge for the ecologically sustainable development of women's knowledge, competence, entrepreneurship is shown. The educational process based on Gender differences and equality contributes significantly to the development of society.*

Keywords: *gender mainstreaming, gender-sensitive, socio-economic analysis, national and universal values, social institutions, competence, entrepreneurship is shown.*

I. INTRODUCTION

It is not surprising that the information age of the 21st century is recognized as such. Nogaku believes that society develops and finds progress, relying on the knowledge and entrepreneurship of the individual. And the educational process, organized on the basis of Gender differences and equality, makes an important contribution to the development of society, it will be able to field as a necessary component of the cultural, socio-economic and environmentally sustainable development of the pupil's personality.

In our country, by the end of the last century, thoughts about gender differences and similarities in the educational process began to be put forward. The fact is that gender is an approach that has arisen as a continuation of feminist theory.

At the conference of UNESCO on October 9, 1998, it was recognized that the purpose of the higher education system is the restoration of society free from violence and oppression. It is noted that in order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to re-develop educational programs using new pedagogical technologies and modern methods. In the newly developed training programs, equality of men and women, as well as gender factors of all subjects were taken into account. These initial attempts, based on world practice, were supported by the UN Development Programme, UNESCO, the Open Society Foundation. As a result, the course of gender studies was introduced into the programs of Moscow State University, Kharkiv University and a number of higher educational institutions of the CIS countries.

Materials of the special session of the UN General Assembly on the theme of "women-2000: gender equality, development and peace" in 2000, recent studies prepared by the World Bank indicate that there is an inalienable link between economic development and gender equality. The important role of this problem in the development of society can be clearly seen in the example of increasing interest in this area in Germany and other European countries in recent years. In some higher education institutions of Uzbekistan, starting from 2001, initiative teachers give lectures covering one or more aspects of gender Research in the form of special courses. Experiments in this regard have shown that students' interest in gender Research is strong.

II. THE MAIN PART

The study of gender studies in higher educational institutions of our republic is not only the formation of the future thinking of specialists on the basis of the latest analytical achievements in the world, but also the promotion of further development of this sphere in the science of Uzbekistan, undoubtedly. Gender differences and similarities are based on taking into account the similarities and differences in the educational activities of girls and boys in the educational process. This, in turn, will help to ensure the effectiveness of the educational process. He or she determines the im-cones of the pupil's personality of this gender.

Studies aimed at taking into account gender differences and similarities between boys and girls are carried out in practice on a somewhat wider scale in gender pedagogy and psychology. This is especially evident in the direction of sexual education and the consideration of spiritual opportunities in this process. Sex-based education is a collection of educational, educational tools that have a comprehensive impact on the preparation of the student for the future life.

Today, gender differences and identity recognition in the educational process are recognized as a natural pedagogical phenomenon. However, there is no scientific interpretation of this phenomenon in didactics. It is clear to all specialists that it is impossible to ensure the effectiveness of the educational result without taking into account the peculiarities of gender differences in the educational process. In particular, psychologists have achieved a number of achievements in this area.

The term Gender was introduced into scientific consumption by American psychologist scientist Stoller in 1968 year, which means "sex". Although sexual relations were previously also actively studied in psychology, the emergence of a new term has created new currents in Social Sciences. Such branches of science as " Gender history", " gender psychology", " gender sides of philosophy", " gender anthropology", " gender sociology "and later" gender pedagogy " were formed.

The concept of "Gender " primarily covers the socio-psychological and pedagogical aspects of the relationship between a man and a woman, a boy and a girl. This concept is connected with new social views and culture. Gender conception is developing in the CIS region as a category of socio-economic analysis. Currently, a number of achievements have been achieved in the implementation of the gender Research course in Russia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Ukraine and other republics of the former Union to the educational programs of higher education institutions. One of the most important achievements in pedagogical science today is the opening of opportunities for teaching on the basis of gender equality and differences. This phenomenon also has a special value in terms of humanization of Education.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes the legal basis for ensuring gender equality in the educational system. On the basis of the new amendment of the law "on Education adopted" in 2020, equal rights of sons and daughters of all educational institutions, choosing a profession are ensured. In the 2004-2005 school years, the number of boys and girls studying at the school was almost the same, with 51% of boys and 49% of girls. In the system of secondary special and vocational education, this discrepancy increases. In academic lyceums, the number of boys is 64% and girls 36%, while in vocational colleges the number of boys is 53%, girls 47%.

The number of male children entering higher educational institutions is also higher than that of female children. This is due to the fact that women and girls with higher education have fewer opportunities to work than men. Because it is assumed that parents believe that the funds

spent on their studies will be effective and will have a negative impact on the family budget. In Uzbekistan, there are problems of gender balance in the higher stages of education, including academic lyceums and higher educational institutions. Since the first years of independence, the Government of Uzbekistan has made significant efforts to eliminate this trend and raise the status of women on all fronts. In the educational process, it is considered as one of the urgent issues to understand the position of boys and girls in society and in the family, to properly prepare them for the life of the family and society. In this sense, the Government of Uzbekistan fully joins the decisions adopted in the final documents of the fourth World Conference on the status of women, which was held in Beijing on September 4-15, 1995. Indeed, in paragraph 12 of this decision:

"We affirm our participation in broadening women's opportunities and improving their situation, including thinking, belief, religion and views, ensuring that moral, spiritual, spiritual and intellectual requirements are met individually or together with others, and that as a result, their life in society is fully manifested in the formation of their potential in accordance with their own desires and wishes."

In paragraph 27, the ideas of "promoting non-stop economic growth by providing women with basic education, continuing education, training in literacy, vocational training and primary medical humanitarian work " are described.

Paragraph 30: "to create broad opportunities for women and men to receive education and medical care and to ensure equal treatment in these areas, to improve the sexual and reproductive health of women, as well as to improve their level of knowledge» thinking about.

III. DISCUSSION

The problem of Gender attracts the attention of philosophers, sociologists, anthropologists, linguists, literary critics, psychologists and educators. The psychological aspects of gender are well-known psychologists Z. Freud, T. Parsons, R. Staller, Sh. Bern, A. Bandura, Simona de Beaver, A. Klima, S. Mining, A. Usmanova, I.S. Klesina, E. Gaziev, O.Abduusattorova, X. R Haydarova, sociological aspects E.Goffman, R.Xaf, A.Kolstkorova, A. Zdravomislova, A.A. Tyomkina, G.K. Zaitsev and A.G. Zaitsev, G.B. Urazalieva, philosophical aspects of Keith West, D. Zimmerman, S.G. Ayvazova, I. Jerebkinas, aspects related to anthropology E.RYarskaya-Smirnova, some aspects of pedagogy L. Shustova, P. Repkina, R. Safarova, G. Lit up in the works of Akramova.

The educational system is of particular importance in society not only as a factor of technological and socio-economic development, but also as an important strategic tool for spiritual and economic development. Therefore, in our independent country, great attention is paid to the sphere of education every year. This task is entrusted to all stages of the educational system: from pre-school educational institutions to the higher stages of Higher Education.

Despite the variety of approaches and points of view in relation to the designation of gender, it is possible to distinguish two concepts. These conceptions are as follows:

- 1) gender social structure theory;
- 2) gender system theory.

The approach to gender from a social point of view will be as follows: from a biological point of view, gender is a set of tasks that are inherent in a particular society to the gender that is decided on, and the specific behavior of both the boy and the girl children, the different manifestations associated with the social norms of interaction.

Introduced by Hof, the boy and the girl represent the spiritual and cultural images of children. In accordance with this approach, gender is represented as a measure of the social relationships that are decided in a particular society. The study of socio-humanities by students in the higher education system promotes the development of social activity of student-girls on the basis of gender approach.

The idea of national independence, fundamentals of meaning, sociology, cultural studies, history of Uzbekistan, pedagogical history, religious studies, which are taught in the higher education system, create an opportunity to increase the social activity of students and perfect the process of adaptation to society. Gender theory approaches in the educational process from a different point of view to the issue of distinguishing characteristics inherent in boys and girls. In this approach, the main differences between the sexes are manifested in their social originality. These differences are formed in society by means of social institutions, norms and cultural views. This is important in the social aspects of gender differences.

Gender stratification is the basis of the development of the socio-pedagogical system of humanism in society and education system. At present, the social activist of students and students-girls of social insitutes in society such as family, education, religion, culture-educational importance in the development of gini increases the effectiveness of this process. One of the most important achievements in pedagogical science today is the opening of opportunities for teaching on the basis of gender equality and differences.

This phenomenon also has a special value in terms of humanitarian education. In the process of realization of this goal, the first task is to improve the existing educational programs using new pedagogical technologies and modern methods. In the improved curricula, it is important that the equality of boys and girls is determined on the basis of gender equality and differences in all disciplines. Such educational process new educational tools-methodical materials and didactic work requires the creation of lanes. In turn, educational and methodical materials should be selected in connection with the means of control.

IV.CONCLUCIONS:

The reforms carried out in the Republic are giving positive results in the economic, social, political, cultural and educational development of our society among the most developed countries of the world. Such changes are carried out consistently in the educational system, as in all spheres. After the country gained its independence, the main task was to restore our values, to realize ourselves, to form a national idea and ideology in the worldview of students, to rebuild the educational system, to prepare specialists that meet all mature and modern requirements.it is important that it is determined on the basis of RG. Such educational process new educational tools-methodical materials and didactic work - requires the creation of lanes. In turn, educational and methodical materials should be selected in connection with the means of control.

At present, radical changes are taking place in the socio-economic and spiritual life of Uzbekistan, the issue of organizing the educational process on the basis of gender equality and differences of the individual should also become a component of pedagogical processes and research. With the help of the educational materials provided taking into account Gender equality and differences, students' observability, design, hypothesis, prediction skills are consistently formulated.

After all, the regulation of social and educational relations between girls and boys has an important pedagogical significance. Because training through its processes, social relations between male and female members of society are decided in perspective.

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